

Reliability and Maintainability Analysis of Table Saw Machine

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Abstract:

Reliability and Maintainability analyses are necessary actions to be taken on machines in order to reduce operation cost and enhance production efficiency. They are among the design attributes of a machine. Therefore, engineers and machine's operators need uphold their standard in order to ensure seamless production over the production cycle, reduce wastage due to downtime and maximize profit. This work considers the reliability analysis and preventive maintenance of a mechanically repairable machine -Table Saw

machine. The inter-failure times of the machine was shown to follow the Burr XII distribution with scale and shape parameters; $\theta = 0.503$ and $\lambda = 0.333$ respectively. Hence, the failure distribution and the reliability indices of the machine were obtained based on the Burr XII failure function using real life data of a Makita MLT 100 Table Saw 255mm (10") 1500W machine. The result shows that the reliability of the Table Saw machine gradually decreases from 0.3758 to 0.3216 within the interval 220 to 626 hours of operation. The mean time between failures (MTBF) is approximately 89.77 hours, indicating that the Table Saw machine operates for about 90 hours of the machine or 9 working days at 10 hours per day before failure. The mean time to repair (MTTR) is approximately 10.34 hours, implying that the machine is typically restored within a working day after failure. The machine has an availability factor, (A_r) of approximately 89.7%, meaning that it is operational for about 95% of the time. The maintainability factor, (M_r) is approximately 10.3%, with a standard deviation time of 312.14 hours indicating that about 10% of the total time is used for repair and maintenance actions.

Keywords: *Reliability, Maintainability, Table Saw machine, probability function, Burr XII distribution.*

Introduction

Every mechanical system (machine) should at all costs be reliable, hence, the reliability study to ascertained the state of well-being and readiness of the operating characteristics of systems over a period of time. Reliability is commonly defined as the probability that a system will remain operational throughout a specific period under defined operating conditions. It is consistently recognized as a pivotal attribute for industrial products and systems. Reliability involves the

analysis of lifespan data, and this data is then employed to estimate, assess, and manage the performance of components, products, and systems. The theories and tools of reliability find applications in diverse fields, including but not limited to electronic and manufacturing products, aerospace equipment, earthquake and volcano forecasting, communication systems, navigation and transportation control, medical treatment, as well as survival analysis concerning human beings and biological species (Weibull, 1977 and Lawless, 1982). Therefore, reliability

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analysis of industrial machine is essential to ensure smooth performance and targeted production run in an industry. Udoh (2018) obtained probability and reliability functions for a locally fabricated cassava grinding machine with weibull failure function which operational efficiency degrades with time and usage. The reliability index as well as other performance measures were obtained. Also, in 2019, Udoh modeled the failure distribution of a welding machine which failure distribution function was shown to follow gamma distribution and the associate operational indices were obtained in order to determine the availability of the machine for production.

A repairable system is a system which can be restored to its original working condition by any maintenance action after failure, Lindqvist, (2006). Guo et al. (2000) surveyed the developments in the generalised models of repairable systems reliability during 1990s, particularly 1995-2000. They noticed a fundamental problem where voluminous complex models were developed but there was an absence of sufficient data of interest to justify the success in tackling real engineering problems. Instead of following the myth of using simple models to face the complex reality, they selected and reviewed some practical models, particularly the stochastic processes behind them. Furthermore, a repairable machine can be repaired once failure happens, but it is vital to assess the risk of unexpected failures in order to improve the system reliability; Khan and Haddara (2003) and Wang, *et al.* (2012). Mettas and Zhao (2005) explored the general renewal processes (GRP) to model and analyze complex repairable systems with various degrees of repair while Nadia and Huda (2014) obtained and compared the classical "maximum likelihood and uniformly minimum variance unbiased" estimators and the Bayesian estimators of the shape parameter, θ and reliability function based on a complete sample when the other shape parameter, λ is known for probability distributions. Lindqvist (2015) dealt with general repair models for repairable systems. He examined ways of modeling the impact of repairs on a system condition. The first strategy was that

repairs impact on the system by the failure intensity, and the second option considers the impact of repairs by performing the time-dependent scale transformation of the governing distribution function.

Maintenance is important in the operation of facilities and equipment in general. It encompasses a range of activities carried out on facilities or equipment to either restore them to good working condition or to ensure they remain in an acceptable working state. It includes technical procedures aimed at achieving and maintaining the satisfactory operation of machines or parts. It serves the primary purpose of ensuring that equipment and facilities can perform their designated tasks as scheduled and under specified conditions. Maintenance helps prevent unexpected failures and disruptions in operations. The first two extreme assumptions or types of maintenance; namely, "as-good-as-new" and "as-bad-as-old," are impracticable compared to imperfect maintenance. This is because the failure nature of repairable systems depends on the repair history of the system, Muhammad *et al.* (2009). Subsequently, Poór et al. (2019) put the changes in maintenance management strategies in the context of industrial revolutions. The article summarizes the characteristics of each industrial revolution and maintenance management approach together with paradigm shifts that accompanied them. Udoh *et al.* (2022) modeled the failure times and other operational characteristics of television transmitter system with sudden but non-constant failure rate to enhance smooth operation of the system. The failure times was shown to follow lognormal distribution. The Probability functions, hazard, reliability functions/indices, availability and maintainability factors were obtained to help describe the failure behaviour and ascertain the performance level of the system.

The Burr XII distribution also known as the Burr Type XII distribution or the Singh-Maddala distribution, is another parametric probability distribution that is used in reliability engineering, survival analysis, and other fields. This distribution is characterized by its flexibility in modeling a wide range of failure patterns, and it

can be especially useful when other common distributions such as the Weibull, exponential, or lognormal do not adequately capture the characteristics of the data (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Burr_distribution). This distribution can exhibit various hazard rate shapes, including increasing, decreasing, bathtub-shaped and constant, depending on the values of the shape and scale parameters. This flexibility makes it a valuable choice when the underlying failure mechanism of a system is not well understood or when the failure data do not conform to a simple parametric model. The selection criteria for the Burr XII distribution can be based on empirical data fitting and statistical goodness-of-fit tests. If this distribution provides a good fit to the observed data and if it makes sense from a reliability and failure mechanism perspective, it can be a suitable choice. Yong (2004) compared the estimates from graphical and maximum likelihood methods of Burr XII distribution. He concluded that the maximum likelihood method generally provides more accurate estimation for the underlying model. However, in case of small sample size data, the graphical estimation is better in terms of the accuracy and estimation errors. It was recommended that a combination of the two estimations method for the parametric estimation is necessary. Al-Noor and Al-Ameer (2014) obtained and compared the classical "maximum likelihood and uniformly minimum variance unbiased" estimators and the Bayesian estimators of the shape parameter, θ and reliability function based on a complete sample when the other shape parameter, λ is known. Para and Jan (2014) introduced a discrete analogue of generalized Burr-type XII distribution using a general approach of discretizing a continuous distribution. Burr XII distribution was suggested as a suitable reliability model to fit a range of discrete lifetime data. Rao *et al.* (2015) estimated the multicomponent stress-strength reliability by assuming the Burr-XII distribution. The research methodology adopted was to estimate the parameters by using maximum likelihood estimation. The reliability was estimated using the maximum likelihood method of estimation, and the results were compared using the Monte-Carlo simulation for

small samples. Zimmer *et al.* (2018) presented the statistical and the probabilistic properties of Burr XII distribution and described its relationship to other distributions used in reliability analyses. They outlined its use as a model for failure data; illustrated the methods for graphical estimation on probability paper and presented examples of its usage. However, just like with other parametric models, it is important to interpret the estimated parameters in the context of the application and the system being studied. Its application gives the reliability practitioners another model for representing failure data, (Zimmer *et al.* 2018). Udoh (2018) modeled the failure rate of an 8HP-PML Gold Engine cassava grinding machine which operational efficiency degrades with time and usage. The failure distribution was shown to follow the weibull distribution function and its performance measures were obtained. Yari and Tondpour (2018) proposed three discrete analogues of the Burr XII-gamma distribution to meet the need of modelling discrete lifetimes in reliability. They investigated estimation of their parameters using three methods (maximum likelihood, moments and empirical). Mazucheli *et al.* (2018) used the discrete Burr XII distribution, obtained by the discretization method proposed by Nakagawa and Osaki (1975), in the analysis of data related to animal production. The data describe the time, in days, from birth to first laying of yellow quail. Almuhayfith *et al.* (2022) considered two failure modes, and failure time data for a hybrid type I censoring scheme. The model parameters were estimated using maximum likelihood and Bayesian methods under a symmetric squared error loss function, whereas the intervals estimation was done with three methods: asymptotic and credible confidence intervals. Besides a simulation study, a real-life data set was taken from individuals who live in an environment with several diseases to underscore the usefulness of the work. De Araújo *et al.* (2023) presented a new autoregressive moving average model based on the τ -th quantile of the Burr XII distribution (BXII-ARMA) since the quantile is less sensitive than the average of heterogeneous populations and also suitable in the presence of outliers. This model makes it

possible to model any quantile by a dynamic structure containing autoregressive terms and moving averages, time-varying regressors, unknown parameters, and a link function. The conditional maximum likelihood method was considered to estimate the parameters and build the confidence intervals of the BXII-ARMA model.

Our interest in this work is to examine the reliability and maintainability functions and indices of a mechanically repairable Table Saw machine to provide information on the state of the machine as well as provide time to repair and time to perform other maintenance actions on the system to avoid failure and wastage.

Assumption of the Study

The assumptions of this study are:

1. The machine experiences random failures.
2. Failures that occur at any given time, t , are distributed continuously and independently.
3. The Failure occurs at the end of time t , based on the machine's lifetime distribution, $f(t)$.

Makita MLT 100 Table Saw 255mm (10") 1500W Machine

This is a mechanically repairable system that doesn't maintain a constant failure rate over time. Instead, it experiences a degradation in operational efficiency as it's used overtime. In essence, this machine deteriorates or wears out with both usage and time. As a result, the primary focus of this work is on assessing the reliability function and relevant maintainability measures for this machine. The reliability function and associated measures provide critical information about the machine's state. They offer insights into when maintenance actions should be performed to avoid failure and minimize wastage. This type of failures are often modeled using the Burr XII distribution. The Burr XII distribution is particularly suitable for systems that do not exhibit a constant failure rate and is known for its versatility in capturing different shapes of failure curves, when other common distributions are not a good fit for the data. The use of Burr XII distribution to model system failure rate can

help engineers and reliability analysts to make informed decisions about maintenance schedules and the expected operational life of the machine, ultimately ensuring its continued functionality while minimizing downtime and waste.

Materials and Methods

In reliability analysis, reliability engineering and survival analysis, choosing an appropriate statistical model for failure times is a crucial decision. A handful of parametric models are often used because they have been shown to be effective in various scenarios.

Model Selection Criteria of failure distribution function

The use of statistical goodness-of-fit tests to assess how well a chosen model fits the data can help in objectively evaluating the quality of the model fit. In many cases, a combination of empirical success, expert knowledge, and an understanding of the failure mechanism has guided the selection of the most appropriate parametric model.

Goodness-of-Fit test for Burr XII Distribution

Table 1 shows the observed and pooled expected frequencies of failure data of Table Saw machine.

To calculate the expected frequencies, we use the formula below;

$$E = N[F(x_j) - F(x_i)]$$

For $0 < t < 120$

$$Recall that F(x) = 1 - (1 + x^\lambda)^{-\theta}$$

$$E_1 = 59\{[1 - (1 + 120^{0.333})^{-0.503}] - [1 - (1 + 0^{0.333})^{-0.503}]\} = 6.3$$

For $120 < t < 240$

$$E_2 = 59\{[1 - (1 + 240^{0.333})^{-0.503}] - [1 - (1 + 120^{0.333})^{-0.503}]\} = 29$$

For $240 < t < 360$,

$$E_3 = 59\{[1 - (1 + 360^{0.333})^{-0.503}] - [1 - (1 + 240^{0.333})^{-0.503}]\} = 8.14$$

Following the same process, we obtain the rest of the expected frequencies:

For $360 < t < 480$: $E_4 = 9.82$

For $480 < t < 600$: $E_5 = 4$

For $600 < t < 720$: $E_6 = 0.96$

Table 1. Table of Observed and Pooled Expected Frequencies

Intervals of Time T	Observed Frequencies (O_i)	Expected Frequencies (E_i)
$t < 120$	5	6.3
$120 < t < 240$	26	29
$240 < t < 360$	10	$8.14 \cong 8$
$360 < t < 480$	12	$9.82 \cong 10$
$480 < t < 720$	6	$5.96 \cong 6$
Total	59	59

Source: Ms Word

The Test Statistic is given by;

$$\chi^2_{\text{test}} = \sum_{i=1}^5 \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i} = 1.494$$

The χ^2 Goodness-of-fit test shows that the distribution of failure rate of the Table Saw machine follows Burr XII distribution at 5% level of significance. This result was validated by the use of Easyfit (5.6) software on Table 2.

Table 2. Extract of Easyfit Goodness-of-fit Test for the Failure Data of Table Saw Machine

Distribution	Kolmogorov Smirnov		Anderson Darling		Chi-squared	
	Statistic	Rank	Statistic	Rank	Statistic	Rank
Burr XII	0.10264	1	0.87318	1	0.62162	1
Log-Logistic (3P)	0.11014	2	0.87596	2	0.7244	2
Dagum	0.11057	3	0.90513	3	N/A	
Weibull (3p)	0.11093	4	0.9133	4	2.3751	3

Source: Easyfit software

The Mean and Variance of a Two Parameter Burr XII Distribution

The probability density function of the two parameter Burr XII distribution is given by;

$$f(x_i; \theta, \lambda) = \theta \lambda x^{\lambda-1} (1 + x_i^\lambda)^{-(\theta+1)}; \theta > 0, \lambda > 0, x > 0 \quad (1)$$

$$Mean = E(x) = \int_0^\infty x f(x) dx = \theta \lambda \int x^\lambda (1 + x_i^\lambda)^{-(\theta+1)} dx$$

$$Let p = (1 + x_i^\lambda)^{-1} \Rightarrow x = (p^{-1} - 1)^{1/\lambda} \text{ and } dx = \frac{-p^{-2}}{\lambda} (p^{-1} - 1)^{1/\lambda-1} dp$$

$$\text{Then, } E(x) = \theta \int (1 - p)^{1/\lambda} p^{\theta-1/\lambda-1} dp$$

By definition of Beta distribution of first kind, (2) can be written as;

$$E(x) = \theta \left[\frac{\Gamma(\frac{1}{\lambda}+1)\Gamma(\theta-\frac{1}{\lambda})}{\Gamma(\theta+1)} \right] = \theta \left[\frac{\Gamma(\frac{1}{\lambda}+1)\Gamma(\theta-\frac{1}{\lambda})}{\theta!} \right] = \theta B\left(\theta - 1/\lambda, 1 + 1/\lambda\right) \quad (2)$$

Similarly, $\therefore E(x^2) = \theta B\left(\theta - 2/\lambda, 1 + 2/\lambda\right)$

Hence,

$$Var(x) = E(x^2) - (E(x))^2 = \left[\theta B\left(\theta - 2/\lambda, 1 + 2/\lambda\right) - \left\{ \theta B\left(\theta - 1/\lambda, 1 + 1/\lambda\right) \right\}^2 \right] \quad (3)$$

Reliability Function of Burr XII Distribution

Reliability, $R(t)$ is defined as the probability in which an item or an entity performs its intended function over a period of time under stated conditions. It is given by;

$$R(t) = -P(T \leq t) = P(T > t) = 1 - \int_0^t f(t)dt$$

For Burr XII with parameter θ and λ ;

$$R(x) = 1 - F(x) = 1 - \left[1 - (1 + x^\lambda)^{-\theta} \right] = (1 + x^\lambda)^{-\theta} \quad (4)$$

Determination of Failure Rate or Hazard Function, $h(t)$ of Burr XII Distribution

The hazard function gives the failure rate of the system immediately after time x . According to Mann *et al.* (1974), the hazard rate is a function of time and has a probabilistic interpretation: namely, $h(x)dx$, represents the probability that a device of age, x will fail in the interval $(x, x + \Delta x)$, or

$$h(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\left(\text{a device of age } x \text{ will fail in the interval } (x, x + \Delta x) \text{ if } \right)}{\left(\text{it has survived upto } x \right)} \Delta x$$

The hazard function, denoted by $h(x)$ is given below;

$$h(x) = \frac{f(x)}{1-F(x)} = \frac{f(x)}{R(x)} = \frac{\theta \lambda x^{\lambda-1} (1+x^\lambda)^{-(\theta+1)}}{(1+x^\lambda)^{-\theta}} = \frac{\theta \lambda x^{\lambda-1}}{1+x^\lambda} \quad (5)$$

The Reliability Indices

The mean time between failures (MTBF)

This measures the predicted time that passes between one previous failure of a system to next failure during normal operation. It is given by;

$$MTBF = \frac{\text{Total operational time}}{\text{Total number of repairs}} = E(X) \quad (6)$$

Availability factor

It is the probability that a system will work as required during a particular period of time. It is given by:

$$A_f = \frac{MTBF}{MTTR+MTBF} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

Maintainability Measures

The mean time to repair (MTTR)

Its timing begins as soon as the repairs starts, and elapses when the operations are restored. To calculate the MTTR, divide the total maintenance time by the total number of maintenance actions over a given period of time as shown below;

$$MTTR = \frac{\text{Total maintenance time}}{\text{Total number of repairs}} \quad (8)$$

The median time to repair (MeTTR)

This is given by:

$$MeTTR = t_{(n+1)/2} \text{ if } n \text{ is odd and } MeTTR = \frac{t_n + t_{(\frac{n}{2})+1}}{2}; \text{ if } n \text{ is even} \quad (9)$$

The variance time to repair (VTTR)

$$VTTR = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(t_i - MTTR)^2}{(n-1)} \quad (10)$$

The standard deviation time to repair (SDTTR)

$$SDTTR = \sqrt{VTTR} \quad (11)$$

Maintainability factor

It is the ease with which maintenance of a functional unit can be performed in accordance with prescribed requirement. It is given by;

$$M_f = \frac{MTTR}{MTTR+MTBF} \times 100\% \quad (12)$$

Estimating the Two-Parameter Burr XII Distribution Using Maximum Likelihood Method

Given the distribution of Burr XII in (1), the Likelihood function is given by:

$$L(\theta, \lambda | x) = \prod_{i=1}^n f(x_i | \theta, \lambda) = \theta^n \lambda^n \prod_{i=1}^n x_i^{\lambda-1} \prod_{i=1}^n (1+x_i^\lambda)^{-(\theta+1)} \quad (13)$$

The natural log of the Likelihood function of (13) is:

$$\ln L(\theta, \lambda; x) = n \ln \theta + n \ln \lambda + (\lambda - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i - (\theta + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \ln(1 + x_i^\lambda) \quad (14)$$

To find the maximum of θ , we take the derivative of (14) with respect to θ and set it equal to zero;

$$\frac{\partial \ln L}{\partial \theta} = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{n}{\theta} - \sum_{i=1}^n \ln(1 + x_i^\lambda) = 0$$

$$\hat{\theta} = \frac{n}{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln(1+x_i^\lambda)} \quad (15)$$

To find the maximum of λ , we take the derivative of (14) with respect to λ and set it equal to zero;

$$\frac{\partial \ln L}{\partial \lambda} = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{n}{\lambda} + \sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i - (\theta + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^\lambda \ln x_i}{1+x_i^\lambda} = 0 \quad (16)$$

$\hat{\lambda}$ can be obtained as the solution of the non-linear equation

$$\frac{\partial \ln L}{\partial \lambda} = \frac{n}{\lambda} + \sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i - \theta \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^\lambda \ln x_i}{1+x^\lambda} - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^\lambda \ln x_i}{1+x^\lambda} = 0 \quad (17)$$

Substituting (15) in (17), we have

$$= \frac{n}{\lambda} + \sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i - \left(\frac{n}{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln(1+x_i^\lambda)} \right) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^\lambda \ln x_i}{1+x^\lambda} - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^\lambda \ln x_i}{1+x^\lambda} = 0$$

Therefore,

$$\hat{\lambda} = n \left[-\sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i + \frac{n}{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln(1+x_i^\lambda)} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^\lambda \ln x_i}{1+x^\lambda} \left(1 + \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln(1+x_i^\lambda)}{n} \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (18)$$

$\hat{\lambda}$ is a fixed-point solution of the non-linear equation, therefore, it can be obtained by using a simple iterative scheme as follows; $\lambda_j = \lambda_{j+1}$ where λ_j is the j^{th} iterate of $\hat{\lambda}$. In order to obtain $\hat{\theta}$ in (15), we assume $\lambda = 0.333$ since $\lambda > 0$ without loss of generality (Panahi and Asadi (2010)).

Results

Burr XII Parameters Estimates of Table Saw Machine

$$\lambda = 0.333$$

From (12), $\hat{\theta} = 0.503$

Estimates of Reliability Indices of Table Saw machine

From (6) and (7), the reliability index - MTBF and availability, A_f were respectively obtained as 89.77 hours and 89.7%.

Estimates of Maintainability measures of Table Saw machine

From (8) to (12), the maintainability measures; MTTR, MeTTR, VTTR, SDTTR and M_f were respectively obtained as 10.34 hours, 232 hours, 97433.49 hours, 312.14 hours and 10.3%.

Probability Functions of the of Table Saw machine using Burr XII Distribution

By using the estimated parameters of Burr XII distribution from our data; $\hat{\theta} = 0.503$ and $\lambda = 0.333$. The failure function, reliability function, $R(t)$, the hazard function, $h(t)$, the failure cumulative function were obtained as shown in Figures 1 - 4.

Discussion

The Reliability Function

With reference to Figure 1, the reliability of the Table Saw machine reduces rapidly within the time interval; 220 to 626 hours with values between 0.3758 and 0.3216. This shows a decrease.

Figure 1. A Graph of Reliability Function against Time of the Table Saw Machine

Source: Minitab 17

The Hazard Function or Failure Rate

Figure 2 is a combination of a decreasing hazardrate of early failure and constant hazard rate of random failure which is the first and second stage of the 'bathtub curve' of the hazard function. The failure rate decreases from point 0.00203 to 0.00044 within the first 330 hours of operation and maintains an

approximately constant failure rate from 330 to 626 hours at point 0.0002.

Figure 2. A Graph of Hazard Function against Time of the Table Saw Machine
Source: Minitab 17

The Failure Distribution Function

Figure 3 shows that the distribution of failure increases from point 0 to 0.63 within the time interval of 0 hour to 240 hours. It increases continually at a rapid rate from 240 to 630 hours at point 0.63 to 0.68 respectively.

Figure 3. A graph of cumulative distribution against time of the Table Saw machine
Source: Minitab 17

The Failure Density Function

The likelihood of the occurrence of failure in the Table Saw machine in Figure 4 decreased sharply from point 0.00090 to 0.00054 within 0 to 106 hours of operation and starts reducing gradually as time increases.

Figure 4. A graph of density function against time of the Table Saw machine
Source: Minitab 17

The Reliability and Maintainability Indices

The mean time between failure of the Table Saw machine $MTBF=89.77$, which implies that the Table Saw machine will be operational for 89.77 hours, approximately 10 working days of 10 working hours per day before failure occurs. Also, the mean time to repair $MTTR=10.34$ hours implies that the machine is restored to normal working condition within one (1) day on the average after failure. The availability factor; $A_f = 89.7\%$ implies that the Table Saw machine is in a working state for 89.7% of the time while the maintainability of the Table Saw machine; $M_f = 10.3\%$, implying that 10.3% out of 100% time of the machine is used for repair and other maintenance actions. In addition, the variance time to repair, $VTR = 97433.49$ hours shows the wide dispersion in the maintenance time which is good for a working machine while the median time to repair shows the midpoint between the least time and the highest time it took to repair the machine.

Conclusion

The reliability and availability indices obtained in this work shows the state of health of the machine at a given time as well as providing guide to maintenance in order of guarantee seamless operation and productivity. This analysis is necessary and should be performed at

given period as an aid to effective maintenance of industrial machines and home equipment.

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